

Effect of Conditioning on Yarn Properties

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Abstract: The fiber strength and elasticity increase the proportion filed with the increase Humidity. It is evident after conditioning the moisture regain % climbs down to 7% on the Day 6. Which is a positive sign for the study. Because with incase of moisture other properties should be lithely change after yarn conditioning. The other parameters like user u%, cv%, thick and thin places/km, tpi, hairiness and csp also changers "it the increasing period of conditioning. The filling stop trials indicated that conditioned yarns ·wove at a lower stop level than unconditioned yarn. However, only yams conditioned on the indirect steam system, at 75-80 degrees Celsius, wove significantly better at the 95 % confidence level.

This research also showed that filling stop levels with ring spun yam are affected to a greater degree the end yams. Slashing procedureds were kept consistent throughout th trial. Arm conditionIng did not affect any of the slashing planometers tested. Because of this, the conditioned warp yarns did not weave at a lower warp stop level. The dye uptake transvalued that conditioned yam absorb less dye than unconditional yarn. The difference in uptake was great enough to result in visible differences indicator the delta measurers.

Keywords: yarn properties, effect of conditioning, effect of yarn conditioning.

1.1. Introduction:

The project work is an important subject matter of textile technology. Here small change creates a new idea, for successfully completion our four years graduate degree in textile technology. We have tried to give fruitful expression.

Our project is "Effects on yarn properties after yarn conditioning".It is very important for i yarn quality. The aim of our project is to test, analyze and discuss the condition of tested result.

In our project work we have analyzed carded cotton yarn. We have tested the sample in NZ

SPINNING MILL LTD, MAKSONS SPINNING MILLS LTD QC Lab. The tested data

were collected before and after conditioning and then analyzed and compared the result. These help us to know about the effect yarn quality and yarn properties due to conditioning.

1.2. Yam conditioning:

Conditioning of yarn was done by a yarn conditioning system. The standard conventional steaming treatment for yarn is chiefly used for twist setting to avoid snarling in further processing. It do not result in lasting improvement in yarn quality the steaming process may fail to ensure even distribution of the moisture, especially on cross - wound bobbins (cheeses) with medium to high compactness the thermal conditioning process of the yam according is a new type of system for supplying the yam package. Thermal conditioning uses low - temperature *armed* steam in vacuum. With the vacuum principle & steam, the yam is treated very gently in an absolutely saturated steam atmosphere. first removes the air pockets from the reinsure accelerated steam penetration &over the atmospheric oxygen to prevent oxidation. The conditioning process of the physical properties of swanned steam or steam (100% moisture ingas state is uniformly moistened by the fats. The great advantage of this process is that the moisture in the form of gas very finely throughout the yam package and does not cling to the yam in the form of drops. This an achieved in any cross -wound bobbins.

ether the yam packages are packed on open pallets cardboard boxes. • increase in single yam elongation and strength

- Constant co efficient of friction
- Better hairiness value
- Free from electrostatic changes
- Yam weight gain up to 1.8%

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- Constant co efficient of friction
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Weaving Mills

- Improves fabric softness
- Less fly generation good size pickup in sizing
- High elongation and strength lead to enhanced production efficiency

Knitting Plant

- Increased productivity due to less unwinding tension
- Fewer needle breakage
- Better performance in cloth formation
- Significant reduction in fly liberation

Materials and Methods

1.4. Different between condition and unconditioned yarn:

The difference between Conventional yam and Prefix Conditioned yam is rather obvious. Conditioned yam gives to you advantages that contribute to enhance production efficiency both at the knitting and weaving Stages. Made Possible by significant increase in single yam elongation, yam Strength, better hairiness value and constant coefficient friction.

Perfect Yarn Condition System is defined to deliver maximum value and incorporate World class standards and is ideal for treating all kinds of Yarn.

1.5. production calculation for loading packages of yarn condition system. No of packages can be loaded 1 carrier =54 packages

2 carrier can be loaded for =1 batch

No of packages can be loaded 1 batch=S4*2=108 packages

For 1 batch unloaded need time =90 min

No of batch can be unloaded for 24 hours =14*60i90=i6

No of batch can be unloaded for 24 hours =16*108=1728 packages

If packages weight =1.2 kg

Production for 24 hours=2073 kg or 2-ton production per day.

1.5. FLOW CHART OF YARN CONDITION SYSTEM:

2.1. Literacy review

Conditioning process:

During processing of cotton fiber from bale to yarn, the moisture content of fiber kept not constant. moisture varies from process to process. Finally for the adjustment of moisture should be conditioning of yarn packages. Also, for maintaining standard weight of the material. Normally capacity of yarn conditioner machine =1.5 ton

<* Vacuum vessel

<* Full with saturated steam

<* Can kept a constant pressure

Normally yarn packages place in a specific trolley and then full packages load in a l. After certain time trolley would be withdrawn from vessel.

Time- 25-30min (Cotton) 45min (Poly) Materials
Temperature Time

Cotton (waxed)

55-60

25

Cotton (Unwaxed) 60-80 20-25

Polyester 80-100 30-45

P/C 80-100 30-45

Viscose 60-65 25-30

Wool 70-80 20-25

2.2. Various types of Yarn Conditioning; machine

1. ELGI ELECTRIC MACHINE

2. XORELLA YARN CONDITIONING MACHINE

3. BLUEMOON MACHINES

4. PREMIUM NEO YARN CONDITIONING Machine

5. OBEM YARN CONDITIONING MACHINE

Lip conditioning MACHINE

Yarn conditioning by ELGI PROFIX 2.3.
Conditionin2 process for various yarns:

1) 100% Polyester yarn: load the yarn in the form cone wound on plastic cone into beam dyeing machine. Introduce steam and raise the temperature to 100° at 3°Cper minutes. Steam for 15 minutes at 100°C followed b 15-minute cooling =1 cycle.

2) 100% Nylon: load the yarn in the form cone wound on platicon in beam dyeing machine. Introduce steam and raise the temperature to 100° at 3° minutes. Steam for 15 minutes at 100°foiled b 15-minute cooling to a temperature of 50°C = 1 cycle. Repeat the le fir 4 time.

3) Silk yarn: load the yarn in the form confound on plate n s in to a beam dyeing machine. Introduce steam and ral the temperature to 70°C per 3° minutes. Steam for 15 minutes at 70° followed b 15 minutes cooling to a temperature for 30°C= 1 cycle . Repeat the cycle for 4 times.

4) Cotton/Lycra (40's Lycra) or Viscose/Lycra(60's): Conditioning the yam as mentioned for silk.

2.4. Information about yarn.

Troposphere has a great impact on the physical properties of textile fibers and yams. humidity and temperature will decide the amount of moisture in the atmosphere. high timidity in different dependent of spinning is not desirable. Mixing has a great impact quality. The stud wasp r:6 100% cotton IS- 1374 and -6 at 40/60 ratio on 30k.h 100%. It v as observed that regain% of the am along with other properties User

U% and V % · thick and paces Vim, IPI Hairiness and CSP also changes. 2.5. Yarn:

Yarn can be defined as a long fine structure. Capable of being assembly d int>rl •d or interlocked into some intermediate production such as ropes cords, wo en fabric, knitted fabrics.

2.6. Moisture regains:

Moisture regain is the percentage of water present in a textile material of one dry wight.

$$MR.\% = WID * 100$$

Here,

Weight of water = w Oven dry weight= D Moisture regain = MR2.7. Moisture content:

Moisture content is the percentage of water present in a textile material of total weight MC%=W/W+D*100

Weight of water= W Oven dry weight= D Moisture content= MC

2.7. Yarn Properties:

1. Yam Evenness
 2. Yarn Unevenness
 3. Coefficient of variation
 4. Index
 5. Yam Imperfections
 6. Yarn Hairiness
 7. Standard deviation of hairiness
 8. Yarn Count
 9. Relative Count
 10. Yarn Twist
 11. Yarn Shape
 12. Yarn Density
 13. Yarn trash
- 2.8. Yarn Evenness:

Non-uniformity in variety of properties exists in yarns. There can be variation twist, bulk strength elongation fineness etc. Yam evenness deals with the variation in yarn fineness This is the property, commonly measured, as the variation in mass per unit length along th yarn, is a basic and important one, since it can influence so many other properties of th yam and of fabric made from it. Such variations are inevitable, because they arise from th fundamental nature of Sires and from their resulting arrangement. Accordingly, there are limits to the yam evenness.

Unevenness/irregularity (Um)

Number that indicates the amount of overall mass variation in % from the mean mass of the sample. Values are based on the normal cut length (1cm).

Application:

- Shows the overall amount of mass variation over the test length.
- It is recommended to replace U m with CV m.

Um-Value Inert,

Long-term irregularity of mass, assigned to a specific cut length value. The cut length depends on toe testing speed. conversion charts for the first and second generation of the USTER.

speed (m/min)	Cut Length
4	0.22m
8	0.45m
25	1.40m
so	2.80m
100	5.60m
200	11.20m
400	22.40m

Application

For comparisons with results of the previous tarter generations. Which did not have the option to set individual cut lengths?

Um-value, half inert (Um hi)

Medium-term irre21 llarity- 11 lass_conversioncharLUTI/ UTI

Speed (m/mim)	Cut Length
25	0.40m
so	0.80m
100	1.60m
- -	
200	3.20m
400	6.40m

Application: For comparisons with results of previous tester generations UT1/UT2, Which did n t ha e the option to set individual cut lengths? This value is mainly used in the filament yam industry.

Index of irregularity Index 1 -

Where:

«

N == average amount of fibers in the yarn cross-section, based on the test parameter entry value

"Fiber fineness" of the USTER TESTER 5.

Application:

- The yarn irregularity index shows how close a yarn actually measured CV_m is to the theoretically achievable CV/w (CV_m). The CV/w depends on the number of fibers in the yarn cross-section.

• Particular fibers have been processed to yarns.

- This way each other.

Similar yarns with different yarn counts can directly be compared with the "% level selection of the thin place column corresponds to the cross-section decrease or increase in yarn.

2.1. O.A. D of PROFIX Nervosa Yarn Unit

- Contamination free yarn - a clean conditioning chamber without water bath ensures purity of the yarn.
- Absolutely free from fungus - yarn is treated cold saturated steam produced from separate energy vessel.
- Uniform moisture gain - up to 95% accumulation ensures uniform penetrations and maximum moisture gain throughout the package.
- 25% extra productivity compared to the same capacity of conventional YCS due to shorter time
- Conditioning chamber is not having water bath or heaters hence it is safe and prevents fire accidents.
- Low maintenance cost.

2.9. Imperfection of Yarn:

Yarn spun from staple fibers contain "IMPERFECTIONS". They are also referred to as frequently occurring yarn faults. They can be subdivided into three groups

1. Thick places
2. Thin places
3. Naps

The reasons for these different types of faults are due to raw material or improper preparation process. A reliable analysis of these imperfections will provide some reference to the quality of the raw material used. The

Coefficient of variation of mass (CV_m)

Numeric value which is a measure of the overall mass variation based on cut length of J cm.

Application:

1. Shows the overall magnitude of mass variation along a material.
2. May show little reaction to long term mass variation.

CV_m 1m., 100m:

Mass evenness at a cut length of 1 m, 3m, 10m, 50m, 100m.

- For analyzing medium and long-term mass variation. The CV(L)-values can be used to evaluate.
- The effectiveness of silver doublings.
- The effect of autodeletes on the irregularity.
- For the recognition of long-term variation which originate in previous processing stages. The same cut lengths can be selected for diagram charts as well.

CV_m inert

Long-term irregularity of mass which corresponds to a specific cut length. The cut length the testing speed.

Chart for UT1/UT2:

Identical to the table figured in position 3 for U% - inert.

Application

- for comparisons with results of the previous tester generations, which did not have the to set specific cut lengths.

C.V half inert

Medium-term irregularity of mass conversion chart for UT1/UT2

Identical to the table figured in position 4 for U_{rn}/hi.

Application

- * For comparisons with results of the first tester generation, which did not have the option » at specific cut lengths. CV, half inert is used mainly in the filament yarn industry.

index:

standard sensitive levels are as follows - Thin place: -50% -Thick place: +50% -Naps: +200%

Thick Place: Cross section size +35% to 100%. Fault length 4-25 mm Thin Place: Cross section size +30% to -60%. Fault length 4-25 mm. Naps: Cross section size +30% to -60%. Fault length 1 mm.

2.11. Control panel

- Equipped with Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) ensure safety of the stored programmers.
- The advanced design of the system does not require stabilizer and back. '11p battery. • Up to 8 se of various programmers can be stored
- Single cycle or Multi cycle (up to 20 steps) programs ·mg 1·s poss1·ble.
- Double protection for total circuitry.
- OPTI N: Interfacing facility for production data available. Auto Platform
- Well - proven automatic platform arrangement make easier for loading and unloading process.
- A special slipping clutch arrangement is provided for safety.
- Chain carrier and Arm movement for feeding and taking out the material from the chamber is interfaced with the PLC. XO-Smart

XO-Select

XO-Select Cylindrical

XO-Select Cubical XO-:MINI XO-DPX XO-Components XO- Applications

Weaving yams

Ultra-fine yarn counts

Sewing thread

30% less connected load

- Up to 25% less energy consumption
- Virtually maintenance free
- Shortest payback
- 100% process reproducibility
- Vessel made of stainless steel
- Shortest delivery time
- designed

CYLINDRICAL

Custom made treatment vessels to meet the most demanding customer needs for both low and high temperature applications up to 140°C can be selected with a broad range of door opening designs and loading systems. 30% less connected load

Up to 25% less energy consumption Virtually maintenance free

Shortest payback

100% process reproducibility Stainless steel vessel

Fully customizable

Fully automatable

wide range of door openings broad variety of loading systems

Fits any size of yarn carriers (palest, trolleys, boxes etc)

Can be fully integrated into existing logistic.

XOAOM

The Xo-Mini is the perfect textile conditioning machine for all laboratory and resale needs.

Its small size and compact design with treatment temperatures up to 140°C makes the XO Mini the ideal tool for all laboratories, Universities and research institutes.

1 .small size and most compact design

2. Shortest Treatment times

3. Fast payback

4. Lowest energy consumption

5. Virtually maintenance free

XO-Applications

Many sizes and configurations, allowing the tailoring to any special requirement the XO-Steamng Process has many applications in textile manufacturing: Relaxing twist setting, pre shrinking, fixation and stabilization of the textile substrate from fiber fabric are typical applications of the XO-Steamng-Process. XORELLA® maintains know how and data bank for these specific pretreatments. For the conditioning antiunification of textile fibers, yams and fabrics with natural moisture retention the Steaming Process produces reliable and consistent results with excellent measurable quality)

2.1. Weaving yams

conditioned yarns are vital

The Vardhman Group commenced its yam conditioning activities in the mid-I 980s from the outset, worked closely with the Swiss XORELLA AG, which developed

this technology and is the leader in the related market. Mr. S.P. Oswal, "Every yam has to be conditioned as otherwise problems arise. The Indian climate is too hot to allow any retained moisture. However, using XORELLA® conditioning machines, we are able to increase the moisture level by 1.5-2.0% and thus attain yarn quality with excellent running characteristics for the subsequent production phases. Yarn conditioning is a must, yarns containing "Lycra" being otherwise impossible to process."

YCS model & Serial Number: 114 / 1500P I 2005

Experimental work/ experimental detail

Effect of time of conditioning on yarn properties:

Trails	program settl1114S to 80min	Before wt	conditionin g After wt
3.3			36.148
	Vac:90% Temp:60° C Time:8mi n		
2	Vac:90% Temp:60° C Time:30min	46.460	47.000
3	Vac:90% Temp:88° C Time:10mi n	60.950	61.850
4	Vac:90% Temp:60° C Time:10min	66.800	74.650
5	Vac:90% Temp:70° C Time:28min	73.550	74.650

Ultra-fine yarn counts

Yarn Conditioning, an important final step in yarn production Correct yarn conditioning has an important impact on the 'quality improvement of cotton

Yarns. It has been established that the strength and elongation properties increase with moisture content of the yarn. This effect is explained by the fact that an increase in the moisture content results in increased swelling of the fiber and in addition of the increase in fiber and fiber elongation values, in a higher fiber to fiber friction in the yarn Xtraordinary XORELLA® conditioning treatment leads to unmatched quality

Starting before chick points

- In the trolley fixed wheels are placed in platform stopper side.
- Compressor air pressure at 6 bar.
- Energy vessel in water level indicator Low-High -Between.
- Inlet water lines of vacuum pump and energy vessel ball valve should be open.
- Check program number for suitable for suitable count's.

> Load the yarn in the form cones wound on paper cones, in to a trolley conditioning machine In yarn conditioning machine we inserted six(6) trolley at a time (per trolley 96 package) Introduce steam raise the temperature to 58° at 45 minutes. After 45 minutes the beams are open out from the conditioning machine. And then the yarn packages are cooled tinder the air at 30 minutes.

3.2. Yarn conditioning by ELGI ELECTRIC machine

Name of the mills & address:

MAKSONS SPINNING MILLS LID.

GOURIPUR. ASHULIA, SAVAR DHAKA.

BEFORE CONDIDONING

Thin than the yarn conditioning is very poor at before

conditioning for Fig: weight of yarn

After conditioning

Overall it is result acceptable for after conditioning so it is yarn weight is low, Thick, Naps ,U% Thin than the yarn conditioning is very high at after conditioning. This a apposite site of after conditioning. After conditioning the stolidity of yam is good. After conditioning all general properties of yarn is good and acceptable.

So after conditioning it converted to high quality yarn. Here all the properties of yam have improved.

This article summarizes the effect of yarn conditioning on several yarn properties like moisture content, tenacity, elongation at break and yarn hairiness. At the early stages of fiber to yarn manufacturing, the range of moisture content in the cotton fiber lies around the standard level but after yarn manufacturing which becomes lowered, which creates several negative impacts on different yarn properties. To avoid this incident, presence of exact amount of moisture in the fibers is ensured through yarn conditioning process. During this research, yarn made from different fiber lots were tested before and after conditioning to analyze how conditioning puts significant impact on moisture content, tenacity, elongation at break and hairiness of yarn. The result showed around 5% increase in moisture content, around 4 to 6 % decrease in hairiness, 12 to 13 % increase in elongation at break, and a significant change in yarn tenacity. Besides these, this article also provides some explanations behind each impact.

Before conditioning for yarn

-Mr	%	CVm%	CVm Om%	CVm Om%	Thin 50% /km	Thick +35% /km	Thick +50%/km +200%	Neps +200% /km	Nq15 +280%/km	Sh	H	Rel. Cote
1	9.11	11.53	2.35	4.0	0.0	219.0	16.0	68.0	11.0	1.79	7.71	0.9
2	9.63	12.19	3.48	22.0	0.0	241.0	32.0	80.0	20.0	1.75	7.49	-1.2
3	9.59	12.17	2.95	15.0	0.0	289.0	30.0	100.0	18.0	1.80	7.80	-2.6
4	9.35	11.87	2.37	7.0	0.0	270.0	26.0	75.0	15.0	1.71	7.43	-0.6
5	9.24	11.73	2.12	13.0	0.0	273.0	28.0	81.0	13.0	1.86	7.74	-0.2
6	9.78	12.89	4.71	31.0	0.0	337.0	48.0	99.0	17.0	1.66	7.31	-4.3
7	9.59	12.19	2.14	21.0	0.0	338.0	35.0	98.0	15.0	1.76	7.54	-1.3
8	9.72	12.34	3.14	12.0	0.0	315.0	31.0	105.0	18.0	1.80	7.46	-1.4
9	8.82	11.19	2.97	1.0	0.0	177.0	21.0	53.0	10.0	1.69	7.35	10.4
10	9.48	12.05	3.05	16.0	0.0	300.0	39.0	108.0	29.0	1.73	7.41	0.4
Mean	9.4332	12.0239	2.93	142		275.9188	30.6	86.7	16.6	1.7535	7.5223	0.0
Stdev	0.4332	0.2039	0.293	142		29.413	20.917	32.5	20	0.26	0.26	3.9

After conditioning for yarn

Why conditioning is needed:

1) High speed spinning machines generate more friction thus giving additional heat to the yarn and as a result of such heat transfer the yarn moisture content is vaporized.

Rising speeds in spinning result in decreased yarn quality for other processes and it is well known that dry yarns have worse properties. Below graph shows the moisture reduction scenario in cotton process (Fig.:a)

2) Moisture in atmosphere has a great impact on the physical properties of textile fibers and yarns. A high degree of moisture improves the physical properties of yarn and it helps the yarn to attain the standard moisture regain value of the fiber. Yarns sold with lower moisture content than the standard value will result in monetary loss. Therefore the aim of yarn conditioning is to provide an economical device for supplying the necessary moisture in a short time, in order to achieve a lasting improvement in quality.

3) Cotton fiber is hygroscopic material and has the ability to absorb water in the form of steam. It is quite evident that the hygroscopic property of cotton fibers depends on the relative humidity. The higher the humidity is more the moisture absorption. The increase in the relative atmospheric humidity causes a rise in the moisture content of the cotton fiber.

1Fig.(a): Cotton process & moisture content

4) The fiber strength and elasticity increase proportionately with the increase in humidity. If the water content of the cotton fiber is increased, the fiber is able to swell, resulting in increased fiber to fiber friction in the twisted yarn structure. This positive alteration in the properties of the fiber will again have a positive effect on the strength and elasticity of the yarn.

5) The yarn curls, meaning that the yarn tries to reach a state of equilibrium in which twists in the opposite direction from the original twist direction balance the yarn's torque. These twists are also called negative twists. In this state of equilibrium, the inner torsional tensions cancel each other out.

6) Although unevenness of yarn contains thick & thin place. The thicker yarns are less twisted than fine ones, the inner tension rises opposite to the yarn size. Further positive aspects of steaming are the reduction of curling and, at the same time, the setting of the physical properties of closeness and extension imparted to the yarn by twisting.

7) The effect of the process gives fibers, yarns or fabric dimensional stability and very often other desirable attributes like higher volume, wrinkle resistance & temperature resistance.

8) Weight gaining is a very useful utilization of yarn conditioning. Increment of weight depends on the conditioning process especially in cotton. Temperatures,

vacuum time, steaming time, types of steam are the main variables of yarn conditioning.

9) Another crucial achievement of conditioning is the development of quality level. The hairiness, unevenness reduces for conditioning.

10) Again the strength & elongation of cotton is more in wet condition, as a result of conditioning the strength also increased. Below figure shows the development.

2Fig.(b): Improvement of strength & elongation for moisture.

Now we will discuss the moisture response of some Traditional fibres:

Moisture in cotton:

As living plant cells, cotton fibers within a growing boll are literally full of water. Water is critical for fiber growth and the availability of water during early boll growth is related to the final length achieved by the fiber. When the boll matures and opens, fibers lose water and equilibrate with the ambient humidity. Both constituents of seed-cotton- fiber and seed - are hygroscopic, for example sensitive to moisture, but to different degrees.

In its mature dried form, nearly 90 percent by weight of the cotton fiber is cellulose. In fact the cellulose found in cotton fibers is the purest form of cellulose found in all plants. The cellulose in cotton fibers is mostly (88–96.5 per cent) cellulose¹. The non-cellulose components (4–12 percent) are located either on the outer layers of the cotton fiber in the cuticle and primary cell wall or inside the residual protoplasm called the lumen. The secondary wall of mature fibers is primarily cellulose in its most highly crystalline and oriented form (Figure c).

3Fig(c): Representation of the structure of a cotton fiber.

Figure (d) shows the structure of the cellulose molecules in cotton. From a physical view point the molecule is a ribbon-like structure of linked six-membered rings each with three hydroxyl groups (OH) on the C2, C3 and C6 atoms projecting out of the plane of the ribbon. As well as providing structural stability the hydroxyl groups allow extensive intermolecular hydrogen bonding with many molecules, including water. The accessibility of water to these hydroxyl groups depends on the spacing between crystal lattice planes. From completely dry state water molecules will form hydrogen bonds with hydroxyl groups that are not already linked within crystalline regions.

4Fig.(d): Assembly of cellulose molecules in a sheet. Hydrogen bonds are shown by dotted lines. Circled carbon atoms; C2,C3 and C6, show location of hydroxyl (-OH) groups.

As humidity is increased, water will be attracted to these accessible hydroxyl groups. In this respect, available hydroxyl groups will ordinarily be located on the surface of crystalline fibrils, a unit of the cellulose crystal structure. The first water molecules to be adsorbed will be directly attached to hydroxyl groups. Later adsorption may occur on the remaining available hydroxyl groups or form secondary layers attached to already adsorbed water molecules.

Again below figure (e) is interesting because it shows the change in density of cotton with changes in moisture content. From the dry state the density of cotton increases as empty space (in proximity of available hydroxyl groups) within the cellulose structure fills with water. Direct adsorption of water molecules onto these hydroxyl groups results in more efficient molecular packing and gives an initial increase in density. The density then decreases as moisture content increases past four per cent, and layers of water molecules in effect dilute the density of the cotton cellulose structure.

5Figure(e): Change in cotton cellulose density (g/cm³) with moisture regain (per cent)

Moisture has important effects on the physical properties of cotton – particularly tensile properties and other property descriptions normalized for weight. The increase in strength with increased moisture content is attributed to the release of internal stresses as hydrogen-bonding is weakened and to the ability of the structure to be pulled into a more oriented form.

In one study, at 55 percent relative humidity, tenacity was 25.8 g/tex and this increased to 29.1g/tex after conditioning at 75 percent relative humidity. Fiber crimp, compress-ability and torsional rotation properties are also affected by high humidity.

Wool:

Wool is an excellent regulator of humidity it can absorb up to 30% of its weight in humidity without feeling damp or breaking. This hydrophilic property of wool allows it to breathe.

Wool is composed of about 97% protein, 2% lipids, and 1% minerals (Onar and Sariisik, 2004). As shown in below figure(f), wool fiber has a so called skin-core structure. In this structure, the inner cortex is hydrophilic, due to the existence of large number of the polar groups it contains. The outer surface is the hydrophobic cuticle. This cuticle cell is about 0.3-0.6 μm thick and approximately 30 μm long.

Exocuticle (rich in disulphide crosslinks – exocuticle A = 35% cystine; exocuticle B = 15% cystine) and the softer endocuticle (3% cystine). The intercellular cement contains only 1% cystine. The cuticle is 10% of the weight of wool, and the cortex is 90%.

6Fig.(f): Structure of wool

Cortical Cells have a complex interior structure that includes:

Twisted Molecular Chain and Helical Coil

These cells are protein chains that are coiled in a helical shape like a spring. The chains are stiffened by hydrogen and disulfide bonds, linking each coil of the helix, helping to prevent it stretching. Though the helical coil is the smallest part of the fiber this little spring gives wool its flexibility, elasticity and resilience; helping wool fabric keep its shape and remain wrinkle free.

Microfibril

These cells make up the units, lying inside the Matrix. The microfibrils are like the steel that is embedded in

concrete to provide the strength and flexibility. The microfibrils contain three right-handed helices wrapped around each other in a left-handed coil where they are held together by more H-bonds and sulfur bridges (protofibril). Nine of these protofibril coils cluster around two more so that the microfibril contains a total of eleven coils each consisting of three α -helices.

Matrix

The matrix consists of high sulfur proteins. This makes the wool absorbent because they attract water molecules. Wool can absorb up to 30% of its weight in water and can also absorb and retain large amounts of dye. The Matrix region is responsible for wool's fire resistance and antistatic properties.

Macrofibril

Inside the cortical cells are the macrofibrils that are made up of bundles of hundreds of the even finer filaments (the microfibrils). These are surrounded by the matrix region.

During steaming the yarn or doubled yarn twist is set. Of course, the morphological structure of the fibers must be considered when equalizing the tensions by steaming. Since the woolen fiber very quickly gets the temperature for breaking up the hydrogen bridges and the steam for hydrolysing the cystine bridges, a relatively quick twist modification is possible which roughly corresponds to the values of an autoclave moderated yarn; however, the steaming quality of the Steamatic steaming process is much better with reference to the evenness of moisture absorption.

Nylon:

Nylons, or polyamides (PA), are high performance semi-crystalline thermoplastics with attractive physical and mechanical properties that provide a wide range of end-use performances important in many industrial applications. It is a polyamide fiber, derived from a diamine and a dicarboxylic acid, because a variety of diamines and dicarboxylic acids can be produced, there are a very large number of polyamide materials available to produce nylon fibers. The two most common versions are nylon 6:6 (polyhexamethylene adipamide) and nylon 6 (Polycaprolactam, a cyclic nylon intermediate). Raw materials for these are variable and sources used commercially are benzene (from coke production or oil refining), furfural (from oat hulls or corn cobs) or 1,4-butadiene (from oil refining). The chemical reactions are as follows.

7Fig.(g): Structure of Nylon

All nylons are hygroscopic (moisture sensitive), which is an important factor to be considered during material pre-selection, parts design, mechanical performance prediction and optimization. In general, the moisture content in nylon is a key variable affecting processing (polymerization, compounding, molding, welding, etc.) and end-use performances (mechanical, dimensional, surface appearance, etc.). The absorbed water in polymer behaves like plasticizer, which affects material properties such as strength, stiffness, and ductility. Water also results in deterioration of electrical properties.

8Fig.(h): Moisture response of Nylon.

Polyester:

Polyester is currently defined as: “Long-chain polymers chemically composed of at least 85 percent by weight of an ester and a dihydric alcohol and a terephthalic acid. Polyester from polyethylene terephthalate is an extremely strong fiber with a tenacity of 3–9 g/d (27–81 g/tex). The elongation at break of the fiber varies from 15% to 50% depending on the degree of orientation and nature of crystalline structure within the fiber. The fiber shows moderate (80%–95%) recovery from low elongations (2%–10%). The fiber is relatively stiff and possesses excellent resiliency and recovery from bending deformation. The fiber has a specific gravity of 1.38. The fiber is quite hydrophobic, with a moisture regain of 0.1%–0.4% under standard conditions and 1.0% at 21°C and 100% RH. It is swollen or dissolved by phenols, chloroacetic acid, or certain chlorinated hydrocarbons at elevated temperatures. Polyethylene terephthalate polyester is highly resistant to chemical attack by acid, bases, oxidizing and reducing agents, and is only attacked by hot concentrated acids and bases. Biological agents do not attack the fiber.

The name “polyester” refers to the linkage of several monomers (esters) within the fiber. Esters are formed when alcohol reacts with a carboxylic acid:

9Fig.(i): Structure of polyester

There are, therefore, many possible variations of the generic polyester fiber. Two that are currently produced commercially are polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and poly-1,4, cyclohexylene dimethylene (PCDT).

Polyester is a smooth fiber with an even diameter. The fiber diameter usually ranges from 12-25 micrometers (10-15 denier). The undyed fiber is slightly off-white and partially transparent. The fibers are approximately 35% crystalline and 65% amorphous.

10Fig.(j): Close up of a polyester fiber

Below graph shows the comparative moisture performance of above four fibers discussed:

11Fig(k): Comparative moisture response

For conditioning steam is required in specific status. Let us discuss about different types of steam.

Types of steam:

If water is heated beyond the boiling point, it vaporizes into steam, or water in the gaseous state. However, not all steam is the same. The properties of steam vary greatly depending on the pressure and temperature to which it is subject.

Saturated (dry) steam results when water is heated to the boiling point (sensible heating) and then vaporized with additional heat (latent heating). If this steam is then further heated above the saturation point, it becomes superheated steam (sensible heating).

Saturated Steam (Dry)

As indicated by the black line in the above graph, saturated steam occurs at temperatures and pressures where steam (gas) and water (liquid) can coexist. In other words, it occurs when the rate of water vaporization is equal to the rate of condensation.

Saturated steam has many properties that make it an excellent heat source, particularly at temperatures of 100 °C (212°F) and higher.

12Fig.(1): Pressure-Temperature Relationship of Water & Steam

Unsaturated Steam (Wet)

This is the most common form of steam actually experienced by most plants. When steam is generated using a boiler, it usually contains wetness from non-vaporized water molecules that are carried over into the distributed steam. Even the best boilers may discharge steam containing 3% to 5% wetness. As the water approaches the saturation state and begins to vaporize,

some water, usually in the form of mist or droplets, is entrained in the rising steam and distributed downstream. This is one of the key reasons why separation is used to dis-entrain condensate from distributed steam.

Superheated Steam

Superheated steam is created by further heating wet or saturated steam beyond the saturated steam point. This yields steam that has a higher temperature and lower density than saturated steam at the same pressure. Superheated steam is mainly used in propulsion/drive applications such as turbines, and is not typically used for heat transfer applications.

It is advantageous to both supply and discharge the steam while in the superheated state because condensate will be generated inside steam-driven equipment during normal operation, minimizing the risk of damage from erosion or carbonic acid corrosion.

Supercritical Water

Supercritical water is water in a state that exceeds its critical point: 22.1MPa, 374 °C (3208 psia, 705°F). At the critical point, the latent heat of steam is zero, and its specific volume is exactly the same whether considered liquid or gaseous. In other words, water that is at a higher pressure and temperature than the critical point is in an indistinguishable state that is neither liquid nor gas.

Supercritical water is used to drive turbines in power plants which demand higher efficiency. Research on supercritical water is being performed with an emphasis on its use as a fluid that has the properties of both a liquid and a gas, and in particular on its suitability as a solvent for chemical reactions

%	%	Properties									
		10m %	40% /km	Thin - 50% /km	Thick +35% /km	Thick +50% /km	Neps +200% /km	Neps +280% /km	Sls	H	Ref. Cent.
52	12.11	2.72	13.0	0.0	295.0	45.0	111.0	24.0	2.09	8.25	
43	12.01	1.88	13.0	0.0	330.0	33.0	107.0	23.0	1.70	7.19	
32	11.82	2.42	7.0	0.0	270.0	25.0	77.0	17.0	1.91	7.92	
58	12.18	2.23	21.0	0.0	371.0	40.0	100.0	21.0	1.69	7.07	
39	11.93	2.22	18.0	0.0	293.0	34.0	88.0	18.0	1.77	7.58	
74	12.35	2.47	21.0	0.0	320.0	39.0	110.0	23.0	1.72	7.22	
90	12.30	2.58	15.0	0.0	346.0	53.0	109.0	30.0	1.76	7.34	
90	12.90	2.16	34.0	0.0	395.0	61.0	131.0	23.0	1.80	7.26	
	1.74	32.0	1.0	370.0	41.0	90.0	18.0	1.80	7.66		
	2.38	16.0	0.0	357.0	36.0	113.0	18.0	1.70	7.07		
							31.5	18.5	1.79	6.8	
								25	7.45	5.2	
									24		

3.10. Effect of Thin lace of conditionin properties:

Graph :Thin place

Thin place

From the annexure we have found that, before heat setting Thin place-50%o=0.0 and after heat setting Thin place-50%=1.

II before conditioning
III after conditioning

Fig. Thin place

si

3.8 •Graph (Unevenness)

Weight per unit length variation, Um%o

From the annexure we have found that, before heat setting Um%=9.4 and after heat setting Um%=9.6

3.8. Graph (Unevenness)

Weight per unit length variation, Um%Lo

From the annexure we have found that, before heat setting Um%=9.4 and after heat setting Um%=9.6

Fig :Weight per unit length variation, Um%.

Effect of Co-efficient of variation of mass (CVm%) of conditioning on yarn properties:

Co-efficient of variation of mass (CVm%)

Graph :Co-efficient of variation of mass (CVm%)
Co-efficient of variation of mass (CVm%)

From the annexure we have found that, before heat setting CVm%=12.02 and after

heat setting CVm%=12.23.

Fig: Weight per unit length variation, Um%.

The effects of conditioning on yarn properties of both ring spun and open end 100 % cotton and cotton polyester yarn and the resultant weaving.

Result and discussion

Because of the endues productivity and speed, air-jet weaving machines are Overcoming more evlde tm today's textile world. However, these increased speeds place greater stresses on filling dyed warp yarns. The process of conditioning yarn offers one possible method for ethnically yarn prefinances on today's high speed weaving machines This research was conducted to detinning the effects of yarn conditioning on yarn

property weaving stop levels, and dye uptake performance.

Four types of yarns were used in this research. They were: 13.5/1 100% cotton and cotton/polyester ring spun, 11.0/1 100% cotton open-end, and 12.0/1 cotton/polyester

open-end yarn. Also, 40.0/1 100% cotton ring spun yarn was used for warp yarn. The yarn were conditioned on two types of conditioners. One conditioner used indirect steam syst and the other used direct steam system. Two temperature levels of 50-55 degrees Celsius and 75-80 degrees Celsius were used in both types of conditioners. The conditioned yarns were tested for single-end strength, single-end elongation, elasticity, torque (liveliness), and hairiness. Also, unconditioned yarns of the same type were tested to provide baseline for comparison. This research also examined how yarn conditioning effects slashing parameter. The 40.0/1 100% cotton ring spun yarns were slashed and tested for size pickup, encapsulation, penetration, and tensile properties.

Finally, the yarn used for warp and filling were knitted into socks and then dyed. The of this was to determine the effect of yarn conditioning on dye uptake and delta Petties. The 13.5/1 1000/4 cotton ring spun yarns and the 12/1 cotton/polyester open were woven as filling on air-jet weaving machines. The warp yarns were all woven

All weaving trials used a plain oxford weave. The yarn tests results revealed that yarn conditioning did not offer strength, elongation, or elasticity. There were some

stances when yarn conditioning creased yarn hairiness, especially for ring spun yarn of the most consistent findings of this research was that conditioning yarn on either system at either temperature level, significantly reduced yarn liveliness. Results indicated that the indirect steam system, operated at a 75-80 degrees Celsius temperature level, exhibited the most reduction in yarn liveliness. The filling stop trials indicated that conditioned yarns wove at a lower stop level than unconditioned yarn. However, only yarns conditioned on the indirect steam system, at 75-80 degrees Celsius, wove significantly better at the 95 % confidence level. This research also showed that filling stop levels with ring spun yarn are affected to a greater degree than open end yarns. Slashing procedures were kept consistent throughout the trial. Yarn conditioning did not affect any of the slashing parameters tested. Because of this, the conditioned warp yarn did not weave at a lower warp stop level. The dye uptake trials revealed that conditioned Yarns absorb less dye than un-Conditioned yarn. The different in dye uptake was great enough to result in visible differences, as indicated by the Delta E values. There were also dye uptake differences between type of conditioner and temperature used. The 100% cotton Yarns exhibited the greatest differences in dye uptake. Tuts 1s contributed to changes the crystalline of the cotton fiber when the heat and moisture of yarn conditioning are applied.

Result & Discussion:

Fig : cylinder

Fig : cylinder Door

Conclusions:

Yarn conditioning has an enormous impact on the physical properties of yarn. From this research work it is

seen that, conditioning provides remarkable increase in, moisture content, elongation at break, and a significant decrease in yarn hairiness. In terms of tenacity, the increase of tenacity values was not so much significant. Researchers who want to do further research on this topic, as well as the people who are concerned with post spinning processes will be benefitted from this article also. Improvement in yarn properties after conditioning show their influences in post spinning processes.

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